

<p>CONTEMPORARY INTERNATIONAL TERRORISM</p>		<p>Political Science</p> <p>Keywords: Terrorism, politics, media, modernism, violence.</p>
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Abstract

As a starting point, for terrorism and organized crime, we can emphasize that with the birth of human society, crimes and deviations in general have arisen, while from the moment the crimes became economic and beneficial interests both materially and in power, they made organized crime to take on greater proportions, especially since the end of this century, it has been turned into terrorist influence. In the following pages, we will mention only some of the causes and appearances of terror around the world. If we start talking about this problem we have to dwell in some short passages while mentioning some of the appearances of international terrorism.

Introduction

The word terrorism is dominant not only in the media but also in the daily lives of every citizen, it may be perhaps one of the most common terms we have ever heard in the media in recent years. Like any other term that is heavily consumed for a certain period, this word has been crystallized as we have a crystallized culture, politics, the state, the intellectual, and so on. All in one word that if asked we find it difficult to respond and give a rational explanation. If we take data from history, the first case will be in Greek mythology, it is where terror is presented as a matter of feeling of evil and chaos. This is the origin of this word which would later degenerate to express violent acts of one group of people against another.

Meaning and History of International Terrorism

History has many examples, but terror, for example, is called the new period of the French Revolution during the 1790s and later. These were the years of Robespier, the inventor of the guillotine; the tool which will later take his life as it took the life of the French royal family before the revolution.

In the early years of the BoA we have the red terror of the Bolsheviks. Modern terror, it was not only in states that were in transition but also in strong and democratic states. Such cases can also be found in America of the 1950s-1960s where we face a fierce violence between activists for racial equality, the black people, and the white Americans. The culmination of this situation was the killing of John Kennedy.¹

¹ Bashkim Dr. Selmani “Krimi i organizuar dhe terrorizmi ndërkombëtar”, pp. 3-78 Universiteti parë privat “FON”-Shkup 2008/09.

The Notion of Terrorism

The word terrorism means: premeditated violence against non-combatant masses in order to influence public opinion to then achieve the blow of objectives of a political, military or ideological nature.² As a result, the words terrorist and terrorize take their meanings. Terrorism consists in committing a crime by an individual, a group, or by a state. Terrorism is used to evoke in humans a sense of fear which in many cases is far greater than the true consequences of the act. These acts have two important targets, the population or departments of a state. The causes of terrorism are political, for the destabilization of a society but also for revenge. Various goals have led to the establishment of various organizations which then through their political or religious messages evoke fear and panic upon the population. Many political ideas have been instrumentalized by the terrorist organization to justify their actions. As a result, terrorist groups are excited about every ideology.

The Origin of Terrorism

Although this word was born in the eighteenth century, its methods have always existed. For example: in the Roman empire the killer group was that of zealots in Ancient Judea, otherwise known as sicarii or zealots, who in a very organized form killed all the wealthy Jews who were suspected of collaborating with the Romans.³

Sometimes, terrorism is used to put pressure. The first to use this type of terrorism was in 1871 the Tier government against the Prussian invaders.

Terrorism of this nature was used by France during the war in Algeria, which fought in the guerrilla style for independence from France led by General De Gol, also the United Kingdom in Northern Ireland.

If terrorism is divided depending on the purpose, there are different ways to carry it out:

- Asymmetrical terrorist techniques.
- Destruction of planes or monuments;
- Suicidal assassination where the terrorist is defined in the name of an issue;
- Obstruction
- Advanced technology which is one of the ways in modern time terrorism
- Urbanization
- Industrialization etc.

² Ibid

³ Harvey Kushner, “*Encyclopedia of Terrorism*”, Sage Publications, 2003, p. 360.

If we rely on these types of methods, we will find that even the way of understanding the methods of terrorism always has a common asymmetry with many other factors which affect the endangerment of general social security.⁴

Comparison of classical guerrilla strategy with the ones of modern times

Contemporary international terrorism is a typical product of the general developments of the twentieth century. Undoubtedly, these developments also influenced the tendency to significantly replace the classic guerrilla strategy with a moderate international terrorist strategy. The main factors that had influenced the emergence and development of contemporary international terrorism are industrialization, high technological development, urbanization, as well as the possibility of free and comprehensive communication between developed and third world countries.

International terrorist currents

All current international terrorist movements can in principle be separated in four main currents:

- *Motivated political movements, which usually have communist or fascist orientation;*
- *Movements characterized by clear nationalist or ethnic orientations;*
- *Movements based on Islamic ideology; and*
- *State-sponsored terrorism*

The members of these terrorist movements should be defined as "international terrorists" by the fact that they cooperate with each other and conduct a coordinated campaign against the "common enemy". It is characteristic that despite their ideological orientation, most of these movements were trained and funded by certain Arab terrorist circles. This also proves the fact that the Arab terrorist structures had in principle supported any force aimed at destabilizing European and American interests. The Soviet Union and other communist states had acted similarly.

However, in parallel with the beginning of the collapse of the Soviet Union and other communist powers in Europe, there was a tendency of declining international terrorist activities. This phenomenon must be seen in the context of the ideological influence that communist propaganda made against communist terrorists in Western Europe. Therefore, only when the communist "comrades" in the Soviet Union and other Eurocommunist countries withdrew from their utopian attempt to create a communist paradise did the extremist revolutionaries of developed countries begin to understand more rationally the developments of the process.

Indeed, the reduction of international terrorist activities, in addition to its effective combat, had also been influenced by the political activities of some states which, by appearing as mediators

⁴ Bashkim Dr. Selmani "Krimi i organizuar dhe terrorizmi ndërkombëtar", pp. 3-78 Universiteti parë privat "FON"-Shkup 2008/09.

in certain terrorist events, had used their authority to resolve peacefully, respectively the avoidance of unwanted consequences.⁵

International postmodern terrorism

In contrast to modern and classic terrorism, in recent years a completely new form of terrorist action has emerged, characterized by the real possibility of terrorist attacks in all parts of the world, with mass killings and the increasing use of a perfect destructive technology.⁶ Usually, postmodern terrorists are people with higher professional education who do not act like modern and classical terrorists, only by the influence of a clear political motive. Postmodern terrorists usually operate from the combined influence of several intertwined ideological and wealth motives, based on strong adventurous feelings and high hopes for coming to power.⁷

Postmodern terrorist hate for this motive, the “Omu Shinrikyo” sect (AUM) in Japan, believing in the prediction of the prophet Asahara, had begun preparations for the production of “Sarin” substances, for the mass poisoning of the population, in order to relieve pain that will be caused during the destruction of the world, which will occur in 1997.⁸ Another feature of postmodern terrorism is the rapid development of small national terrorist groups into powerful multinational terrorist organizations, which thanks to the destructive attacks and the professional level of the actors, which is also achieved through their adequate education (Tokyo 1995, the 9/11 attacks against the US, etc.).⁹

Transnational Character of International Terrorism

Under international law, if an event, process, action, or phenomenon takes place between two or more states, then that phenomenon is treated as “international” (between states). Whereas, when such a phenomenon crosses the boundary of one state and develops in other states, it is called transnational (passes from one state to another).¹⁰

The study of the transnational character of international terrorism would undoubtedly enable not only the clear understanding of this specific criminal phenomenon, but also the real danger and consequences that this phenomenon could bring to the international legal order.

⁵ Krahaso: Brogan Patrick, *Die Unruhe der Welt, Die Enzyklopädie der Krisen und Konflikte unserer Zeit*. Darmstadt 1990, pp. 618, 623, 626.

⁶ M. Funke, *Internationaler Terrorismus, Westeuropa ist gefordert, Die politische Meinung*, Nr. 1/1986, p.43.

⁷ Chimelli Roudolph, *Die “Action Directe” schreckt Frankreich, botuar në librin: Dieter Schröder, Terrorismus, Gewalt mit politischem Motiv*, München 1986, p.117.

⁸ Gertrud Brücher, *Postmoderner Terrorismus*, Barbara Budrich Verlag, Opladen 2004, pp. 22–33

⁹ While Curcio was in prison, the leadership of the Red Brigades was taken over by Mrs. Cargol, who was killed on 9.06. 1975 during a conflict with the police. Compare: Hans Josef Horchem, *Terror in Europa, Akteure und Hintergründe - Gegenstrategien, Beiträge zur Konfliktforschung*, Nr. 1/1987, p.31.

¹⁰ Manfred Mols/Hans-Joachim Lauth/Christian Wagner (Hrsg.): *Politikwissenschaft: Eine Einführung*. Paderborn-München-Wien-Zürich, 2001, pp. 24-42.

International terrorism in the context of its own transnationality is presented, both in the geographical regions involved in terrorist violence and in the regions in which the various terrorist formations are distributed, respectively.¹¹

Various terrorist groups, defined as transnational actors, force various state actors to take various legal and diplomatic reactions and measures against them. The totality of these intertwined, internal and external (international) actions, at its core is a process, which is manifested as a phenomenon, namely as a transnational policy. For the best understanding of this phenomenon, we give the following example: - Under international law, Palestine Liberation Organization (PLO) although it was not a state (it was not even a terrorist organization) had its own official representations, even at diplomatic levels in many countries of the world. For years this organization, namely the various war formations within it, from different positions and fronts waged war against Israel and other states, which were not pro-Palestinian. With various spectacular actions they tried mainly to actualize and internationalize their national cause. This had undoubtedly affected not only the solidarity of various international masses, but in some cases also the identification of certain non-Palestinian individuals and terrorist groups with the position of the Palestinian people. From this solidarity and awareness, a structured network of international terrorist cooperation was formed. In some cases, efforts have been made by various non-Palestinian inspired groups to copy Palestinian terrorist actions and implement them in other countries. Both these international influences and the acquired diplomatic digestment by the PLO had strongly put forward the international discussion "pro or against the Palestinian issue". Mostly related to this problem, thus depending on the political definition of different political states or entities, various neutral states were also involved in the Palestinian conflict (in forms of providing various financial or technical assistance)¹²

The transnational dimension of international terrorism is always conditioned by the influence of various social, political and economic factors. In reality, the danger of this phenomenon lies not only in the transnational dimensions taken, but rather in the ability of terrorists to exploit such dimensions in terms of breaking a certain state or international system. This means that the threatening potential of international terrorism is always in relation to the objective circumstances of transnationality and the purpose, respectively the ability for international terrorist action. In such cases, there are usually three difficult situations to calculate, as follows:

International terrorism, exercised by various overseas mechanisms with all its dynamism, is advancing as a transnational pseudosystem within the international political system. In this context, the distinction of national terrorism from the international one is difficult.

¹¹ Ulrike Pesch, *Aspekte des internationalen Terrorismus als transnationales Problem*, Bonn 1977, p.247.

¹² Attia Ahmed, *Der Nahost - Konflikt, Aussichten für Krieg und Frieden*, in: *Europa archiv*, Bonn 1975, Folge 6, Jg. 30, pp.189-200.

Here international terrorism, legitimized as a victim of certain state aggression, is usually presented as a strategy of indirect influence in terms of fostering the other party's reckless reactions.

International terrorism, as such, has at its disposal numerous international and transnational elements, which at the same time strengthen their international importance. In this way, "transnational terrorism, carrying its conflict to other regions as well, brutally violates the political boundaries of neutral states. This transfer of political violence, international terrorism always justifies the revolutionary goal of violently changing the system of political attack."¹³

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¹³ Crenshaw-Hutchinson, Martha, Transnational Terrorism and World Politics, The Jerusalem journal of International relations, Vol.1, Nr.2, p.10, cited according to: Georgias Kaouras, Terrorismus, Frankfurt am Main 1993, p.81.